

AN AD HOC COMPARISON OF THE HIGHER SCHOOL CERTIFICATE PERFORMANCE ACROSS GREEK ORTHODOX, JEWISH AND ISLAMIC SCHOOLS AS WELL AS CATHOLIC AND STATE HIGH SCHOOLS IN SYDNEY IN 2023

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to compare final year performance across 30 Greek Orthodox, Jewish, Muslim, Catholic and State high schools in New South Wales in 2022. The success rate or proportion of subjects with high scores (Band 6, 90-100) was the criterion. All three systems (Greek Orthodox, Jewish and Muslim) performed well above the median success rate for schools in the State (5.47%). The overall success rate for Greek Orthodox colleges was below that of the other ethnic groupings; Overwhelmingly, the Jewish schools had a superior performance in the Higher School Certificate. Greek Orthodox colleges and Catholic schools had a higher success rate than the State school systems. Greek Orthodox colleges had a marginally lower success rate than the Catholic schools.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Jewish, Muslim, Catholic, State Schools, Higher School Certificate, schools, Australia

I. INTRODUCTION

This brief report compares the performance of the three full-time Greek Orthodox colleges firstly with three Jewish schools and eight Islamic schools in the final Higher School Certificate examination in New South Wales in 2022. A second comparison is with eight Catholic Schools in similar locations to the Greek Orthodox colleges and eight State schools also in areas adjacent to the Greek Orthodox schools. Of the 30 schools surveyed, 20 did not rank in the top 150 schools in the State.

The results are aggregated so that no school is identified unfairly. No claim is made that the analysis is perfect or entirely unbiased as it is based on limited data from 30 schools at a point in time and under widely differing circumstances.

For the reader who is unfamiliar with the school system in New South Wales, secondary schooling may be seen in broad terms as comprising selective schools based on academic merit, elite private schools catering to higher socioeconomic status, independent private schools such as the ethnic schools, the Catholic education system and the State schools. The Higher School Certificate is the final Year 12 qualification in

secondary school and the high scores on a subject or course are Band 6 or 90-100.

The analysis is mainly in terms of the success rate which is defined as the percentage of subjects examined that resulted in high scores (90-100). By way of background, the median success rate for the 30 schools was 8.69%.

II. COMPARISON OF GREEK ORTHODOX, JEWISH AND ISLAMIC SCHOOLS

The comparison between Greek Orthodox, Jewish and Muslim schools is apt because they represent ethnic communities and their descendants. They represent distinct religious groupings. The results for the comparison between Greek Orthodox, Jewish and Muslim are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Comparison of Greek Orthodox, Jewish and Islamic Schools

Schools	No. of students	High scores	Entries	Success rate
Greek Orthodox	166	100	892	11.2%
Jewish	269	474	1510	31.4%
Islamic	589	487	3011	16.2%

Column 1 lists the background of school. Column 2 shows the number of students (it is an estimate of the number of HSC students based on students who completed English, the compulsory subject). Column 3 indicates the number of high scores (the numbers of Band 6 scores, the highest band of performance). Column 4 indicates entries (the number of courses examined at a school, or the number of students times the number of subjects). Column 5 shows "success" or the percentage of entries (i.e., courses or subjects) that resulted in high scores.

Some straightforward conclusions were drawn from this first comparison:

(a) All three systems (Greek Orthodox, Jewish and Muslim) performed well above the median success rate for schools in the State (5.47%);

(b) The overall success rate for Greek Orthodox colleges was below that of the other ethnic groupings;

(c) Overwhelmingly, the Jewish schools had a superior performance in the Higher School certificate.

III. COMPARISON OF GREEK ORTHODOX, CATHOLIC AND STATE HIGH SCHOOLS

The results of the comparison with Catholic and State schools are shown in Table 2 yields a different picture.

The Greek Orthodox colleges and Catholic schools had a higher success rate than the State school systems. Unfortunately, none of the State schools sampled had a best rank in the top 150 schools.

TABLE 2

Comparison of Greek Orthodox, Catholic and State Schools

Schools	No. of students	High scores	Entries	Success rate
Greek Orthodox	166	100	892	11.2%
Catholic	962	719	5461	13.1%
State	603	141	3010	4.7%

Secondly it was concluded that the Greek Orthodox colleges had a marginally lower success rate than the Catholic schools. The overall results are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall success rate (%) in the Higher School Certificate for different religious groups

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

These results have another aspect beyond comparisons of school systems. The findings are consistent with an earlier report on the performance of Jewish, Muslim and Greek Orthodox students on NAPLAN (National Assessment Program Literacy and Numeracy) in 2011. In that report it was concluded:

Overall, Jewish schools were performing at a high average level and Greek Orthodox colleges were around average. For the most part, the Islamic schools were below the national average (there are exceptions). (Athanasou 2013, p. 14)

The results are also in line with the analysis of educational levels from the Census data in Australia, where it was reported:

In terms of the influence of a religion, there is evidence that faith interacts with educational achievement. Overall, Hinduism and Judaism have higher levels of educational achievement than Greek Orthodox but also the other faith groups (Buddhism, Other Christian, Islam, Secular/No religion). It is especially the case for Hinduism, where they rank highest for graduate qualifications combined (49.3% for postgraduate, graduate). The relationship, however, is more complex than a simple linear comparison and may involve a cocktail of sociocultural, ethnic, migration and policy factors (Athanasou, 2022, p. 3)

It is not considered fair to contrast such differing school systems merely in terms of whether one type of school is better than another. Besides which, there is considerable variability within groups. For instance, two out of the three Greek Orthodox colleges did not rank in the top 150; six out of the eight Muslim colleges did not rank in the top 150; and four out of the eight Catholic schools did not rank in the top 150. This was the advantage of aggregating results rather than making school-by-school comparisons.

Quality of teaching and other resources play a role in overall success but these preliminary results confirm a longstanding differential in educational achievement. It is considered tentatively that there are fundamental differences between groups, and that in a sense, religion interacts with educational achievement. Such a finding is not overly remarkable but it reinforces the view that there are longstanding elites” (Clark 2014, p. 10).

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